

their calli, when subcultured, turned into roots and further proliferation of calli occurred. In all remaining wild species, plantlets developed through embryoid germination. A high frequency of plant regeneration was observed in *O. nirvana* (see figure, b) and *O. rufipogon* (Acc. 104311), whereas low frequency of plant regeneration was observed in *O. rufipogon* (Acc. 104308) and *O. longistaminata*. Embryogenic calli derived from *O. eichingeri* cultured on the same regeneration media failed to regenerate. Root initiation was observed after transferring shoots to growth hormone-free MS medium (see figure, c). Regenerated plants were grown successfully in the field (see figure, d) and seeds were harvested. This system of plant regeneration from embryogenic callus can provide a useful material for the improvement of rice by use of plant biotechnology. ■

Callus induction and plant regeneration from shoot base explant of different wild species of *Oryza*.^a Jaipur, India.

Wild species of <i>Oryza</i>	Callus induction		Plant regeneration		
	Explants planted (no.)	Explants responding (no.)	Calli planted (no.)	Regenerating calli (no.)	Mean±SE
<i>O. meridionalis</i> (Acc. 101147)	42	32	24	NR ^b	-
<i>O. meridionalis</i> (Acc. 101148)	35	35	26	NR	-
<i>O. rufipogon</i> (Acc. 104308)	36	24	24	11	15.0 ± 1.63
<i>O. rufipogon</i> (Acc. 104311)	37	25	25	16	50.60 ± 3.26
<i>O. eichingeri</i> (Acc. 105152)	47	22	21	NR	-
<i>O. nivara</i> (Acc. 101994)	33	33	30	22	26.66 ± 6.80
<i>O. longistaminata</i> (Acc. 101211)	45	31	30	11	2.60 ± 0.24

^aCallusing medium LS + 2.5 mg 2,4-DL⁻¹; regeneration medium MS + 2.0 mg BAP L⁻¹ + 0.5 mg NAA L⁻¹. ONR = no response; SE = standard error; - = no value.

Anther culture of indica/Basmati rice heterotic F₁ and F₂ hybrids and selection of desirable double haploid lines

J. S. Rohilla, J. B. Chowdhury, N. R. Yadav, V. K. Chowdhury, and R. K. Jain, Plant Tissue Culture and Genetics Engineering Laboratory, Genetics Department, CCS Haryana Agricultural University, Hisar, India; K. R. Gupta, Rice Research Station, Kual, India

Anther culture has been useful for the introgression of desirable traits into breeding populations of rice. We have been working on the transfer of dwarfness, defense against brown plant-hopper attack, and resistance to bacterial blight, from indica rice varieties to Basmati rice. This study included 12 indica rice varieties with one or more of the above mentioned desirable traits, six Basmati rice cultivars/breeding lines, and 31 heterotic F₁/F₂ hybrids obtained from different indica / Basmati crosses. Basmati rice parents included Basmati 370, Basmati 385, Pusa Basmati 1 (semidwarf), and advanced breeding lines (HBC5, HBC19, and

HBC143) derived from Taraori Basmati. Panicles were collected from nethouse plants when the distance between flag leaf and penultimate leaf was 4-5 cm. Anthers were cultured in 9 cm petri dishes containing 30 ml N6 and MO19 media supplemented with either 2.0 mg NAAL⁻¹, 1.0 mg kinetin L⁻¹, and 0.5 mg 2,4-DL⁻¹, or 1.0 mg kinetin L⁻¹ and 2.0 mg 2,4-DL⁻¹. MO19 is a modified MS medium which contains 3,134 mg KNO₃L⁻¹, 320 mg (NH₄)₂SO₄L⁻¹, 540 mg KH₂PO₄L⁻¹ and lacks NH₄NO₃. The media contained 40 g sucrose L⁻¹. Cultured anthers were subjected to a cold treatment at 10°C for 10 d and incubated under dark at 24±1°C. Data were recorded on percentage of anthers forming calli after 60 d. Microcalli at 2-4 mm diam were transferred to a modified MS medium containing 0.5 mg NAA L⁻¹ and 1.0 mg each of BAP and kinetin L⁻¹, kept under fluorescent light of 50 µE m⁻²s⁻¹. Data were recorded on calli regenerating green and /or albino shoots after 30 d. Shoots were rooted and hardened in one-half strength MS medium supplemented with 0.25 mg NAAL⁻¹ and 2.5 mg multieffect tri-

azole L⁻¹ (MET, CNRRI, Hangzhou, China). All the media were semi-solidified using 0.25% (w/v) phytagel (SIGMA, USA). Regenerated plants were transferred and grown to maturity in the nethouse.

Representative data are shown in the table. An advanced indica rice breeding line IET12012 showed a high frequency of androgenic calli formation (5.5%) as well as green plant regeneration (10 plants per 1000 anthers). In general, F₂ hybrids responded better to anther culture than F₁ hybrids. The F₂ hybrids involving IET21012 as the female parent were responsive to anther culture. Basmati rice genotypes were less responsive. Anthers from the F₁ indica/Basmati hybrid populations involving HBC19 produced a greater number of embryogenic calli and green plants than those from Basmati 370. A sufficient number of green plants could be obtained from some F₁/F₂ heterotic hybrids and transferred to the greenhouse.

The success of transplantation of regenerated green plants to soil conditions during late February to end of

Anther culture response of indica/basmati heterotic F₁ and F₂ hybrids.

Cultivar/hybrid	Anthers cultured (no.)	Anthers forming (no.)	Calli-regenerating shoots (no.)		
			Albino	Green	Albino/green
<i>Cultivar/breeding line</i>					
Basmati 370 ^a	4200	119 (2.8) ^b	30	6	5.0
HBC5 ^a	4000	130 (3.0)	31	1	31.0
HBC19 ^a	3700	90 (2.4)	8	0	0.0
Pusa Basmati 1 ^a	4700	99 (2.1)	24	1	24.00
HKR239	4700	122 (2.6)	18	3	6.0
HKR86-104	2200	46 (2.1)	0	0	0.0
DM25	1900	65 (3.4)	13	1	13.0
PR106	2300	51 (2.2)	0	0	0.0
IET12012	2400	131 (5.5)	56	25	2.3
<i>F1 hybrid</i>					
HKR86-104/Basmati 370 ^a	3900	101 (2.6)	55	2	27.5
HKR239/Basmati 370 ^a	1600	39 (2.4)	17	1	17.0
DM25/HBC19 ^a	1600	71 (4.4)	54	11	4.9
<i>F2 hybrid</i>					
HKR86-104/Basmati 307 ^a	1600	81 (5.1)	41	7	5.9
PR106/Basmati 307 ^a	1600	57 (3.6)	37	10	3.7
IET2012/HBC5 ^a	3000	171 (5.7)	65	40	1.6
IET12791/HBC5 ^a	1600	67 (4.2)	53	9	5.9
DM25/HBC19 ^a	2600	113 (4.4)	39	6	6.5
HKR86-104/HBC19 ^a	1600	69 (4.3)	26	6	4.3
IET12791/HB19 ^a	1600	62 (3.9)	25	8	3.1
Pusa Basmati 1 ^a /HBC19 ^a	2400	96 (4.0)	22	14	1.6

^aBasmati rice cultivar. Values in parentheses are percentages.

March was of the order of 60-65%. Several of the anther-derived plants had greater number of productive tillers and greater panicle length. On an average, 70% of the plants transferred showed spikelet fertility and set seeds except in case of PR106/Basmati 370 where none of the anther-derived plants produced seeds.

One of the 51 anther-derived plants (designated as AC36) from F₁ DM25/HBC19 hybrid showed exceptionally desirable agronomic characteristics. AC36 had an average of 12.6 productive tillers, a panicle length of 26.2 cm, and 62 filled grains per panicle. This line maintained its Basmati aroma and had a length-breadth ratio of 5.3:1.0 compared with 4.9:1 in HBC19. AC36 had a 1,000 seed weight of 26.4 g compared with 21.1 in HBC19 and 17.7 in DM25. In this generation, however, none of the plants showed the dwarf characteristic of the DM25 parent. ■

Evaluation of rice hybrids in varying environments

C. Lavanya, R. Vijaykumar, and B. Sitadevi, Agricultural Research Station (ARS), Maruteru, West Godavari District, Andhra Pradesh 534122, India

Rice varieties cultivated in coastal areas of India are highly season-specific. Most of them are suitable either for wet (WS) or dry seasons (DS), but a few are suitable for both seasons. Nitrogen fertilization in WS is limited by the problem of lodging caused by frequent rains or storms. Commercial exploitation of heterosis depends on identification of hybrids adapted to variable weather and N levels. Thirty rice hybrids were evaluated in five environments at two N levels in DS, 60 and 120 N (E1, E2) and three in WS, 30, 60, and 120 N (E3, E4, and E5) (see table). They were derived from five CMS lines (IR46830A, IR54752A, IR54754A, IR58025A, and IR62829A) and six restorer lines (WGL3962,

Standard heterosis for grain yield of top 10 heterotic rice hybrids in five environments.^a

Hybrid	Dry season			Wet season	
	E1	E2	E3	E4	E5
IR54752 A/Pratibha	79.6**	74.9**	37.5**	81.7**	46.2**
IR54754 A/Swarna	30.8**	46.8**	58.5**	45.9**	28.7**
IR58025 A/Swarna	67.5**	129.3**	42.9**	112.1**	57.8**
IR58025 A/Vajram	39.9**	77.1**	74.3**	51.1**	49.4**
IR62829 A/Vajram	58.6**	75.5**	50.0**	58.3**	51.9**
IR54754 A/WGL 3962	28.3**	8.7	21.1**	19.2**	34.5**
IR54754 A/Vajram	45.3**	50.2**	48.2**	44.8**	15.3
IR58025 A/WGL 3962	102.2**	32.8**	57.9**	46.8**	15.9
IR62829 A/WGL 3962	81.6**	57.9**	52.1**	32.2**	6.6
IR62829 A/WGL 3962	76.7**	-27.2**	73.4**	69.8**	42.4**
Range of standard heterosis in 30 F ₁ s	-72.2 to 102.2	-78.6 to 129.3	-38.5 to 74.3	-47.2 to 112.1	-65.5 to 57.8

^aE1=60 kg N ha⁻¹, DS; E2=120 kg N ha⁻¹, DS; E3=30 kg N ha⁻¹, WS; E4=60 kg N ha⁻¹, WS; E5=120 kg N ha⁻¹, WS.

Swarna, Vajram, Pratibha, IR36, and IR64). The trial was carried out under an irrigated system at the ARS.

The mean yields of hybrids were generally higher in DS (806 g m⁻²) than in WS (725 g m⁻²). Standard heterosis for yield ranged from -72.2 to 129.3% over IR64 in DS and from -65.5 to 112.1% over Swarna in WS (see table). The hybrids developed using IR58025A as

female parent exhibited a wider range in yield, and standard heterosis ranged from -62.3 to 129.3%. Most of the hybrids performed better in one or the other season whereas some performed better in both seasons.

Five hybrids—IR54752A/Pratibha, IR54754A/Swarna, IR58025A/Swarna, IR58025/Vajram, and IR62829A/Vajram—gave superior performance in